

9th Bubble and Drop Conference

June 11-16, 2023 | Lublin, POLAND

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MARIA CURIE-SKŁODOWSKA UNIVERSITY

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Scientific Program

Thursday, 15 th June 2023	
10.00-10.45	<p style="text-align: center;">Plenary Talk</p> <p>Georgi Gochev, Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry Polish Academy of Sciences, Cracow, Poland</p> <p><i>„Predicting the stability of protein foams: a case study on β-lactoglobulin”</i></p> <p>Chair: Eleni Kalogianni</p>
10.45-11.15	<p>KN8: Elena Mileva</p> <p><i>Self-assembly of Antennary Oligopeptides in Aqueous Environment: Fine-tuning and Applications</i></p>
11.15-12.15	<p style="text-align: center;">Poster session + Coffee break</p>
	<p style="text-align: center;">nanoPaInt special session</p>
	<p>Chair: Eva Santini</p>
12.15-12.35	<p>NP1: Seforah Silva</p> <p><i>Spreading behavior of trisiloxane surfactants on hydrophobic and hydrophilized polypropylene films</i></p>
12.35-12.55	<p>NP2: Galina Makarikhina</p> <p><i>Effect of lateral forces on adsorption and maximal coverage of nanoparticles on oppositely charged interface.</i></p>
13.00-14.00	<p style="text-align: center;">Lunch</p>
	<p>Chair: Piotr Warszyński</p>
14.00-14.20	<p>NP3: Abboud Mohammad</p> <p><i>Nanosuspension Rheology Measurement using Drop Impact onto a Hard Sphere</i></p>
14.20-14.40	<p>NP4: Carlo Carbone</p> <p><i>Interfacial dilational rheology of a water-soluble non-ionic triblock copolymer: does ionic strength affect it?</i></p>
14.40-15.00	<p>NP5: Schon Gabriel Fusco</p> <p><i>Dynamics of Water Drops on Vibrating Surfaces</i></p>
15.00-15.20	<p>NP6: Emily Zholkovskiy</p> <p><i>The Cell Model Approach in Electrodynamics, Fluid Mechanics and Electrokinetics of Nano-Dispersed Systems</i></p>
15.20-16.00	<p style="text-align: center;">Coffee break</p>
	<p>Chair: Tatiana Gambaryan-Roisman</p>
16.00-16.20	<p>NP7: Ana Costa</p> <p><i>Dry coating on anode active materials: influence of wettability on particle interaction and adhesion in lithium-ion batteries</i></p>
16.20-16.40	<p>NP8: Mikołaj Zaleski</p> <p><i>Core@shell nanowires for conductive inks and pastes</i></p>
16.40-17.00	<p>NP9: Iván Navarro Arrebola</p> <p><i>Solid Foams from TiO₂ and TiO₂+Glass Nanoparticles</i></p>
17.00-17.20	<p>NP10: Leonardo Ruiz-Martínez</p> <p><i>Capillary suspensions from aqueous two-phase systems</i></p>

Solid Foams from TiO₂ and TiO₂+Glass Nanoparticles

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Solid foams characterised by hierarchical pore sizes are suitable in applications requiring large surface areas, such as fluid filtration or catalysis. They can be obtained by direct foaming of dispersions of amphiphilic NP-surfactant complexes and consolidated by the gel-casting method [1-2]. The process is scalable and suitable to obtain solid foams from several types of NP. Both the interfacial and bulk properties of the precursor dispersion contribute to control the final structure of the solid foams. Based on previous studies addressing the interfacial properties of mixed amphiphilic and hydrophilic NPs [3], we are extending this method to obtain multicomponent solid foams. In particular, solid foams made of mixtures of borosilicate glass and titania NPs have been fabricated, that join the suitable mechanical resistance and transparency of a foamed glass structure with the photocatalytic features of titania [1,4].

SEM images from TiO₂+CTAB (left) and glass/TiO₂+CTAB (right) porous materials

References

- [1] M. Vaccari et al. *Catalysis Communications*, 171 (2022) 106527.
- [2] D. Zabiegaj, et al., *Colloids and Surfaces A*, 473 (2015) 24-31.
- [3] S. Llamas, et al. *Colloids and Surfaces A*, 575 (2019) 299–309.
- [4] M. Vaccari et al., This Conference.

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Solid Foams from TiO_2 and TiO_2 +Glass Nanoparticles

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